

SEARCH FOR NEW LOCAL ANAESTHETICS. PART I

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Several diethylamino-, piperidino- and morpholino-acetyl and -propionyl derivatives of 2-methyl-5-isopropylaniline have been synthesised and their local anaesthetic activity studied.

Basic amides and basic anilides, like basic esters having lypolytic and hydrophilic moieties, show local anaesthetic activity (Miescher, *Ber.*, 1928, 61, 730; Hoffer, *Klin. Woch.*, 1929, 8, 1249; Lofgren, *Chem. Abs.*, 1937, 31, 7854; Gaid *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1940, 17, 400, 619). Strong local anaesthetic activity has been shown by basic anilides where lypolytic moiety is substituted by alkyl groups (Lofgren *et al.*, *Chem. Abs.*, 1948, 42, 6378; 1949, 43, 1021). Xylocaine (*o*-diethylamino-2:6-dimethylacetanilide), reported by Lofgren *et al.* (*loc. cit.*), has been found to possess a very high local anaesthetic potency, both in surface as well as in infiltration anaesthesia, without much toxicity. It appears that the increase in number of alkyl groups raises the activity of the compounds. No attempt appears to have been made to substitute the lypolytic moiety with higher alkyl groups. With this object in view, compounds of the general type (I) have been synthesised for studying the local anaesthetic activity.

These compounds were synthesised by chloro-acylation of 2-methyl-5-isopropylaniline with chloroacetyl chloride, α -chloropropionyl chloride and β -chloropropionyl chloride. 2-Methyl-5-isopropylaniline was prepared in better yields by nitrating *p*-cymene ("Org. Synthesis", 1941, 21, 96), followed by reduction of the nitro compound (Wheeler and Smithey, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 43, 2613). The chloro-acetylated product was then condensed with the secondary amine. The bases being liquid were characterised through their solid derivatives.

EXPERIMENTAL

o-Chloroacetyl-2-methyl-5-isopropylaniline (I: R = H; n = 1; B = Cl).—Chloroacetyl chloride (13.5 g.) in dry benzene (20 c.c.) was gradually added to 2-methyl-5-isopropylaniline (14.9 g.) in dry benzene (20 c.c.). The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for an hour. Benzene was distilled off and the residue washed with water,

followed by sodium bicarbonate solution. The chloro-acetylated product on chilling in ice came out as a white solid which was crystallised from 80% alcohol and then recrystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60°-80°) in small needles, m.p. 84°, yield 13.5 g. (Found: N, 6.5. $C_{12}H_{16}ONCl$ requires N, 6.2 per cent).

Hydrochloride of N-Piperidinoacetyl-2-methyl-5-isopropylaniline (I:R = H; $n = 1$; B = piperidino).—A mixture of the above chloro compound (2.3 g.) and piperidine (1.7 g.) in absolute alcohol (20 c.c.) was refluxed for 4 hours. Alcohol was distilled off and the residue treated with sodium bicarbonate solution. It was then dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid, filtered and again basified to liberate the base. The oily base was extracted with ether and converted into its hydrochloride. The hydrochloride was crystallised from dry acetone-dry petroleum ether (b.p. 60°-80°) mixture, m.p. 189°. (Found: N, 8.8; Cl, 11.5. $C_{17}H_{26}ON_2.HCl$ requires N, 9.01; Cl, 11.43 per cent).

Perchlorate of diethylaminoacetyl-2-methyl-5-isopropylaniline (I:R = H; $n = 1$; B = diethylamino) was prepared in a similar manner by heating the chloro compound (2.3 g.) and diethylamine (1.5 g.) in absolute alcohol. The base and also its hydrochloride came out to be sticky masses which could not be purified. The base was therefore extracted with ether and to the ethereal extract a few drops of perchloric acid added. The solution was triturated thoroughly when a solid mass separated. It was crystallised from acetone, m.p. 234° (decomp.). (Found: N, 7.4. $C_{16}H_{26}ON_2.HClO_4$ requires N, 7.7 per cent).

Hydrochloride of N-morpholinoacetyl-2-methyl-5-isopropylaniline (I:R = H; $n = 1$; B = morpholino) was similarly prepared by heating morpholine (1.8 g.) with the chloro compound (2.3 g.). The base came out to be an oil which was converted into its hydrochloride. The hydrochloride was crystallised from dry acetone-dry petroleum ether (b.p. 40°-60°) mixture, m.p. 150°. (Found: N, 8.79. $C_{16}H_{24}O_2N_2.HCl$ requires N, 8.96 per cent).

β -Chloropropionyl-2-methyl-5-isopropylaniline (I:R = H; $n = 2$; B = Cl) was obtained by treating 2-methyl-5-isopropylaniline (14.9 g.) with β -chloropropionyl chloride (15.2 g.) in the usual way. It came out to be an oily substance and therefore it was distilled under vacuum. The product distilling at 198°-200°/5-7 mm. was collected (9.5 g.).

Hydrochloride of β -N-piperidinopropionyl-2-methyl-5-isopropylaniline (I:R = H; $n = 2$; B = piperidino) was prepared by refluxing a mixture of piperidine (1.7 g.) and the chloro compound (2.4 g.) in absolute alcohol for 5 hours. The base, an oily substance, was isolated in an analogous manner. It was converted into its hydrochloride in the usual way and the hydrochloride crystallised from dry acetone in white needles, m.p. 104°. (Found: N, 8.3. $C_{18}H_{28}ON_2.HCl$ requires N, 8.62 per cent).

β -Diethylaminopropionyl-2-methyl-5-isopropylaniline Picrate (I:R = H; $n = 2$; B = diethylamino).—The base was prepared by heating diethylamine (1.5 g.) and the foregoing chloro compound (2.4 g.) in absolute alcohol. The base was an oily substance and its hydrochloride was also found to be hygroscopic. It was therefore converted into its picrate in benzene solution and the picrate was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 96-97°. (Found: N, 13.2. $C_{17}H_{28}ON_2.C_6H_5O_7N_3$ requires N, 13.8 per cent).

α -Chloropropionyl-2-methyl-5-isopropylaniline (I : R = CH₃ ; n = 1 ; B = Cl) was obtained by treating 2-methyl-5-isopropylaniline (14.9 g.) with α -chloropropionyl chloride (15.2 g.) in the usual way. The product was crystallised from petroleum ether (b. p. 60°-80°) in needles (11.0 g.), m.p. 74°. (Found : N, 5.65. C₁₅H₁₈ONCl requires N, 5.84 per cent).

Perchlorate of α -N-piperidinopropionyl-2-methyl-5-isopropylaniline (I : R = CH₃ ; n = 1 ; B = piperidino) was prepared in an analogous manner by heating the foregoing chloro compound (2.4 g.) with piperidine (1.7 g.). The base came out to be a semi-solid mass and its hydrochloride was also found to be sticky which could not be crystallised. The perchlorate of the base was prepared in the usual way and crystallised from absolute alcohol-ether mixture in white needles, m.p. 158°. (Found : N, 7.8. C₁₈H₂₆ON₂.HClO₄ requires N, 7.2 per cent).

The preliminary investigations on the local anaesthetic activity of the hydrochloride of N-piperidinoacetyl-2-methyl-5-isopropylaniline in 2% solution shows better surface anaesthesia (42 minutes) on rabbit cornea than cocaine (38 minutes) in 2% solution. Hydrochloride of β -N-piperidinopropionyl-2-methyl-5-isopropylaniline shows lesser activity than the acetyl analogue. The compounds are being studied further for their pharmacological activity.

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